

Repositories of AI Literacy Resources (RAILR): A Repository-Based Concept for Sustainable and Equitable Access to AI Literacy Resources

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1. Background and Rationale

GenAI tools, particularly large language models, are designed to produce natural language outputs based on patterns learned from vast training data (Hofmann et al., 2024; Microsoft, n.d.). However, they are not inherently reliable and may generate incorrect, biased, or entirely fabricated information (Huang et al., 2025; Massenon et al., 2025; Dierickx et al., 2026). GenAI tools are prone to hallucination or hasty generalisation, meaning they can give responses or provide content that appear convincing but are actually incomplete or entirely false (Joseph et al., 2025; Dierickx et al., 2026; Østergaard & Nielbo, 2023), largely because their outputs are based on statistical probability and pattern matching from training data. While these tools can improve efficiency, users should have adequate knowledge to use them responsibly and understand their limitations in order to avoid the propagation of false information. This has become a serious challenge, as researchers and students are among the most active users of these tools (Chugunova et al., 2026; Freeman, 2025), and this has increased the need for AI literacy across research and academic institutions.

Librarians are well placed to respond to this challenge, and they are increasingly called to champion AI literacy in their institutions (Porter, 2026). Their expertise in information retrieval, source evaluation, and, more broadly, digital literacy positions them to help researchers and students understand the limits, biases, and ethical implications of these tools. However, the pace of AI development (Henley Business School, 2025; Sousa, 2025) shows that librarians also need sustained support, training, and access to high-quality resources if they are to lead AI literacy efforts effectively in their institutions.

Structured training programmes, workshops, fellowships, and institutional initiatives on AI literacy are useful, but they are unlikely to reach all librarians. Even where such programmes exist, participation may be limited by time, location, cost, or institutional capacity. A more equitable approach is therefore needed. One feasible approach would be to develop Repositories of AI Literacy Resources (RAILR) that would remain freely accessible. This is particularly important because structured AI literacy capacity-building programmes, wherever situated, would likely not reach all librarians and, by extension, researchers, students, teachers, and self-learners beyond academic and research settings. With RAILR, they can have continued access to the training resources used in such programmes, even if they are unable to participate directly. It is intended to complement formal training programmes by ensuring that the resources used in such programmes remain openly available for continued reuse and adaptation in order to support ethical and responsible engagement with AI systems and protect human agency.

UNESCO's AI competency frameworks for students and teachers (UNESCO, 2024a; UNESCO, 2024b) also emphasise ethical AI use, the protection of human agency, and the development of the knowledge needed to engage responsibly with AI systems. These goals can only be realised when students and teachers have access to high-quality AI literacy resources.

2. The Concept of RAILR

RAILR refers to openly accessible, repository-based infrastructure that is FAIR-aligned and designed to host, preserve, curate, and make discoverable AI literacy resources for learning, teaching, adaptation, localisation, and equitable access across institutions globally.

It does not refer to a single fixed repository or platform, but rather to a broader repository model for ensuring that AI literacy resources remain accessible, reusable, and adaptable.

The resources included within RAILR should help users understand and critically engage with AI systems, especially generative AI, in ways that support responsible use, responsible reading, critical evidence appraisal, research integrity, and the protection of human agency. RAILR therefore provides a structured approach to preserving and sharing AI literacy resources in ways that prioritise openness, discoverability, reuse, adaptation, localisation, and long-term access.

3. Why RAILR Is Needed

Access to Training Resources: AI literacy is becoming an institutional necessity, yet access to training remains uneven. Many librarians, and by extension students and researchers, particularly in less-resourced institutions, may not have opportunities to participate in formal AI literacy programmes. RAILR can help address this gap by providing continued access to the resources used in such training, thereby extending learning beyond formal training opportunities and supporting librarians in building the knowledge and competencies needed to lead AI literacy efforts in their institutions.

Resource Fragmentation: AI literacy resources such as guides, frameworks, policies, teaching slide decks, lesson plans, webinar videos, books, AI research papers, and similar materials are scattered across a wide range of platforms, making them difficult to find, reuse, and adapt, especially where clear terms for adaptation or reuse are absent. Bringing such resources together in more organised and discoverable ways can also reduce duplication of effort by enabling institutions and educators to reuse and build on existing high-quality materials rather than repeatedly creating new ones.

Research Visibility and Curation: Researchers globally are increasingly conducting research on AI systems and tools and disseminating their findings through various publication outlets, including journals and other platforms where these outputs remain widely scattered or fragmented. RAILR would make it easier to curate such outputs in more structured ways and help users access research relating to the specific aspects of AI they want to understand. It can also support institutions in curating and showcasing AI-related research outputs emerging from their institutions to showcase their productivity in AI research.

Discoverability: RAILR can also strengthen the discoverability of AI literacy resources through proper metadata standardisation, persistent identifier integration, and interoperable repository configurations. Together, these can enhance the discoverability and utilisation of AI literacy resources, as utilisation is dependent on reliable discoverability.

Updating and Version Control: The pace of AI development means that one-off training programmes organised by institutions will be insufficient. AI literacy and competence require continuous learning and reflection (Chiu et al., 2024). A repository-based approach can extend learning beyond the duration of individual capacity-building programmes or training and can provide continued access to the resources used in such programmes or training. It can also support the updating of resources over time. As new findings emerge and new guidance on AI tools is developed, revised versions of resources can be added, making it easier to keep resources current and relevant.

Adaptation and Localisation: A RAILR can also make adaptation and localisation easier. When contributors deposit resources such as teaching slide decks, lesson plans, and guides with clear reuse and adaptation licences, other users and institutions can more easily adapt them.

Equity and Distributive Justice: Without equitable access to AI literacy resources, existing inequalities in research support may widen further. RAILR therefore responds not only to questions of access, but also to inclusion, equity, and distributive justice. Distributive injustice occurs when people are excluded from access to useful resources (Babu et al., 2025). With RAILR, librarians, researchers, teachers, and students can have access to quality AI literacy resources irrespective of their institutional or geographic location.

Preservation and Long-Term Access: Many currently accessible AI literacy resources may become inaccessible when a project ends, a grant concludes, or a website is taken down or becomes inactive. RAILR can provide more reliable long-term access to such resources.

Cost-Effectiveness for Institutions: Developing high-quality AI literacy resources is expensive and time-consuming. RAILR would reduce duplication and give institutions the opportunity to access resources developed in other institutions and adapt such resources, which would save institutions significant time and money.

AI Literacy and Compliance: Article 4 of the EU AI Act requires organisations that provide or deploy AI systems to ensure that staff and other relevant persons have a sufficient level of AI literacy (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689, 2024, art. 4). As AI systems become more widely used by researchers, teachers, students, and professional staff in academic institutions, compliance expectations may continue to evolve, and institutions may be required to demonstrate or ensure AI literacy among their communities or provide structured AI literacy training. With RAILR, institutions can access quality AI literacy and training resources that they can reuse in such training or make available to their communities.

Open Pedagogy and Student-Created Resources: Open pedagogy is a learner-centred approach in which students act as co-creators of knowledge rather than just consumers (Maultsaid & Harrison, 2023). Since students are among the most active users of AI systems, especially generative AI tools, drawing on their experiences would be valuable. RAILR can function as a repository for AI literacy resources produced by students. Institutions can curate and share AI literacy resources created by students. This would allow students to move beyond being users of available AI literacy resources and become active contributors by creating or co-creating resources based on their own experiences of using AI systems and openly licensed AI literacy materials.

4. Target Users and Beneficiaries

- i. academic and research librarians
- ii. students and teachers
- iii. researchers and research support staff
- iv. library schools and LIS educators
- v. university teaching and learning centres
- vi. scholarly communication practitioners
- vii. self-directed learners

5. Resource Types in RAILR

RAILR may include training manuals, textbooks, e-books, teaching slide decks, lesson plans, policy templates, workshop recordings, AI frameworks, reading lists, case studies, checklists, guides for evaluating AI outputs, responsible prompting guides, resources on hallucination and bias, copyright and intellectual property guidance resources, multilingual or locally adapted teaching materials or guides, and institutional AI-related research outputs, as well as other similar resources.

6. RAILR Framework

6.1 Core Principles of RAILR

The core principles of the Repository of AI Literacy Resources (RAILR) are grounded in the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016; GO FAIR, n.d.) and the Repositories of Open Educational Resources (ROER) concept (Santos-Hermosa et al., 2017), and are further shaped by standards of equity, quality, ethics, and sustainability. These will help ensure that AI literacy resources are findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable, and of high quality.

I. Findable

AI literacy resources in RAILR should be assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers, such as DOIs or ARKs, and described with rich, machine-readable metadata to enable easy discovery by both humans and machines.

II. Accessible

Resources should be retrievable through standardised, open, and free communication protocols. Metadata should remain accessible even when the underlying resource is updated, moved, or no longer available.

III. Interoperable

Resources and metadata should use formats, standards, and vocabularies that support exchange, integration, and use across platforms and systems.

IV. Reusable

Resources should be released with clear, open licences, such as Creative Commons licences, that permit reuse, adaptation, and localisation. They should include detailed provenance information and meet domain-relevant standards.

V. Quality and Curation

Resources should undergo appropriate quality review or expert curation, with attention to relevance and usefulness.

VI. Sustainability

Resources, metadata, and repository infrastructure should remain available beyond the duration of specific training events, grants, or projects.

VII. Human Agency and Critical Judgment

Curated and newly produced AI literacy resources should strengthen informed, ethical, and critical human engagement with AI systems and tools rather than encourage passive reliance on them.

6.2 Scope

RAILR is not a single fixed repository or platform. Rather, it is a repository-based concept that can be implemented in different ways depending on institutional, national, organisational, or project capacity. It may support both the preservation of existing AI literacy resources and the curation of newly produced resources. It may be implemented through different repository arrangements depending on institutional, organisational, national or regional goals or capacity.

6.3 Implementation Forms

RAILR may take the form of an institutional-centric repository model or a shared model, including:

- i. a dedicated thematic repository;
- ii. a special collection within an existing institutional or disciplinary repository;
- iii. a shared institutional, national, or community-governed repository;
- iv. an openly maintained repository linked to institutions, organisations, projects, or communities of practice.

6.4 Quality, Governance, and Sustainability Considerations

Implementation of RAILR in any of its forms would require governance arrangements that support sustainability, quality, and trust in relation to the standards expected of trusted digital repositories. A trusted repository is expected to provide reliable, long-term access to the resources it holds for its designated communities (Center for Research Libraries & OCLC, 2007). A well-structured governance arrangement would help realise this. A community-informed governance model may be especially appropriate, particularly for cross-institutional, national, or regional implementations, as this would help ensure that such repositories remain responsive to diverse needs.

7. Conclusion

By implementing RAILR, institutions and organisations can move beyond one-off AI literacy training programmes or workshops towards a more sustainable, equitable, and open approach to AI literacy capacity

building. RAILR would help ensure that high-quality AI literacy resources remain accessible for continued learning, reuse, adaptation, and localisation.

8. Attribution

RAILR (Repositories of AI Literacy Resources) is a concept introduced by Femi Qudus Arogundade. Open adoption, adaptation, and collaboration are encouraged, provided that clear attribution is given to this original concept and to its author in any substantial reuse, implementation, or derivative development based on this concept.

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References

- Babu, Y., Mishra, P., Kumar, A., Pandey, C. S., & Pandey, S. (2025). Epistemic injustices and curriculum: Strategizing for justice. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 11, 101220.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2024.101220>
- Center for Research Libraries, & OCLC. (2007). Trustworthy repositories audit & certification: Criteria and checklist. Center for Research Libraries. <https://www.crl.edu/sites/default/files/2025-01/trac.pdf>
- Chiu, T. K. F., Ahmad, Z., Ismailov, M., & Sanusi, I. T. (2024). What are artificial intelligence literacy and competency? A comprehensive framework to support them. *Computers and Education Open*, 6, 100171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeo.2024.100171>
- Chugunova, M., Harhoff, D., Hölzle, K., Kaschub, V., Malagimani, S., Morgalla, U., & Rose, R. (2026). Who uses AI in research, and for what? Large-scale survey evidence from Germany. *Research Policy*, 55(2), 105381. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2025.105381>
- Dierickx, L., Opdahl, A. L., Bjerknes, F., & Lindén, C.-G. (2026). What is a fact in the age of generative AI? Fact-checking as an epistemological lens. *Information, Communication & Society*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2026.2630697>
- Freeman, J. (2025). Student generative AI survey 2025 (Policy Note 61). HEPI.
<https://www.hepi.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/HEPI-Kortext-Student-Generative-AI-Survey-2025.pdf>
- GO FAIR. (n.d.). FAIR principles. <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>
- Henley Business School. (2025). The AI high: Feeling optimistic but overwhelmed - How UK workers really feel about the advancement of AI in the workplace.
https://assets.henley.ac.uk/v3/fileUploads/The_AI_High_FOBO_report_this_is_the_final.pdf

- Hofmann, M., Burch, G. F., & Burch, J. J. (2024). Harnessing the power of large language models. *ISACA Journal*. <https://www.isaca.org/resources/isaca-journal/issues/2024/volume-1/harnessing-the-power-of-large-language-models>
- Huang, L., Yu, W., Ma, W., Zhong, W., Feng, Z., Wang, H., Chen, Q., Peng, W., Feng, X., Qin, B., & Liu, T. (2025). A survey on hallucination in large language models: Principles, taxonomy, challenges, and open questions. *ACM Transactions on Information Systems*, 43(2), Article 42, 1–55. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3703155>
- Joseph, J., Jose, B., & Jose, J. (2025). The generative illusion: how ChatGPT-like AI tools could reinforce misinformation and mistrust in public health communication. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 13, 1683498. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2025.1683498>
- Massenon, R., Gambo, I., Khan, J. A., Agbonkhese, C., & Alwadain, A. (2025). "My AI is Lying to Me": User-reported LLM hallucinations in AI mobile apps reviews. *Scientific reports*, 15(1), 30397. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-15416-8>
- Maultsaid, D., & Harrison, M. (2023). Can Open Pedagogy Encourage Care? Student Perspectives. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 24(3), 77–98. <https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v24i3.6901>
- Microsoft. (n.d.). How generative AI and LLMs work. Microsoft Learn. <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/dotnet/ai/conceptual/how-genai-and-llms-work>
- Østergaard, S. D., & Nielbo, K. L. (2023). False Responses From Artificial Intelligence Models Are Not Hallucinations. *Schizophrenia bulletin*, 49(5), 1105–1107. <https://doi.org/10.1093/schbul/sbad068>
- Porter, B. (2026). Libraries as AI literacy leaders. *Information Matters*. <https://informationmatters.org/2026/01/libraries-as-ai-literacy-leaders/>
- Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act). (2024). Official Journal of the European Union, L, 2024/1689. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj/eng>
- Santos-Hermosa, G., Ferran-Ferrer, N., & Abadal, E. (2017). Repositories of Open Educational Resources: An Assessment of Reuse and Educational Aspects. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 18(5). <https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v18i5.3063>
- Sousa, N. (2025). Ethical and practical implications of AI in academic library research. *IFLA Journal*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03400352251391753>
- UNESCO. (2024a). AI competency framework for students (F. Miao, K. Shiohira, & N. Lao). UNESCO. <https://doi.org/10.54675/JKJB9835>
- UNESCO. (2024b). AI competency framework for teachers (F. Miao & M. Cukurova). UNESCO. <https://doi.org/10.54675/ZJTE2084>
- Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J. W., da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers, R., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., ... Mons, B. (2016).

The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3, 160018.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>